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Abstract:

Finding and relocating a particular point of interest on a microscope slide is a frustrating and time-consuming task endured by microscopists from a wide spectrum of disciplines. The appearance of microscope slides, called finders, gridded with independent alpha-numeric reference systems that provided readings exportable to other microscopes partially mitigated this problem. But these devices operate in cumbersome fashion, by repeatedly having to replace both sample and finder slides whenever a point of interest is to be referenced or relocated. The England Finder Calculator (EFC) is a simple software tool that allows users to easily transform x/y coordinates of their specific microscope into coordinates of the England Finder, the gridded microscope slide most extensively adopted by microscopists. This tool should contribute to the standardization of an independent reference system for microscope users.

Key words:

England Finder, Microscope, Relocation, Software